

K-Br system under pressure: synthesis of unconventional stoichiometric compounds

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Abstract:

The search and synthesis of unconventional stoichiometric compounds has become one of the most active areas of high pressure research in recent times. Although several such compounds have been predicted theoretically, very few have been realized experimentally. The notable examples of such compounds are NaCl₃, Na₃Cl, lithium polyhydrides and KCl₃. The experimental realization of more such compounds will enhance our scientific knowledge of the related solid state chemistry. In the present study we report the synthesis of two new stoichiometric compounds, namely KBr₃ and KBr₅ at high pressures in the K-Br system. Two independent experimental techniques namely, diamond anvil cell (DAC) based Raman spectroscopy and x-ray diffraction measurements were employed to detect and confirm the formation of the new compounds. A room temperature chemical reaction between KBr and Br₂ resulted in the formation of an orthorhombic KBr₃ (*SG: Pnma*) at ~ 2.0 GPa. Further compression lead to the formation of a monoclinic KBr₅ (*SG: P2₁*) at ~ 6.0 GPa. This is the first ever experimental synthesis of a 1:5 stoichiometric compound in the alkali halogen system. Formation of KBr₅ was accompanied by an anomalously large pressure (> 2GPa) increase inside the sample chamber and it remains stable up to the highest pressure (24 GPa) of our study. Furthermore, high-pressure (14–20 GPa) and high-temperature (> 1500 K) laser heating experiments showed the decomposition of KBr₅ into a trigonal KBr₃ (*SG: P-3CI*) and Br₂ with a large volume reduction. First-principles structural searches using the USPEX code in combination with VASP code were carried out to solve the composition and related crystal structures.

Keywords: High Pressure Synthesis, x-ray diffraction, Raman spectroscopy, Laser heating

Reference:

1. N N Patel, A K Verma, A K Mishra, M Sunder and S M Sharma, Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys., 19 (2017) 7996.